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Predicting 30-day Mortality for Patients with Acute Heart Failure Who Are in the Emergency Department: A Cohort Study

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29 **Abstract**

30 **Background:** Physicians in the emergency department (ED) need additional tools to stratify patients with acute
31 heart failure (AHF) according to risk.

32 **Objective:** To predict future mortality from data readily available on ED admission.

33 **Design:** Prospective cohort study.

34 **Setting:** 34 Spanish EDs

35 **Participants:** 4867 consecutive ED patients admitted during 2009-2011 for the derivation cohort and 3229
36 patients admitted in 2014 for the validation cohort.

37 **Measurements:** Candidate risk factors and 30-day mortality.

38 **Results:** We found 13 independent risk factors in the derivation cohort and combined them to form an overall
39 score, which we call the MEESI-AHF (Multiple Estimation of risk based on the Emergency department Spanish
40 Score In patients with AHF) score. This score predicted 30-day mortality with excellent discrimination (c-
41 statistic=0.836) and calibration (Hosmer-Lemeshow P = 0.99), and it provided a steep gradient in 30-day
42 mortality across risk groups (<2% mortality for patients in the 2 lowest risk quintiles and 45% mortality in the
43 highest risk decile). We confirmed these characteristics in the validation cohort (for example, c-
44 statistic=0.828). Multiple sensitivity analyses failed to find important amounts of confounding or bias.

45 **Limitations:** The study was confined to a single country. Participating EDs were not selected randomly. Many
46 patients had missing data. Measuring some risk factors was subjective.

47 **Conclusion:** This tool has excellent discrimination and calibration, and it was validated in patients different
48 from the patients used to develop it. We think physicians can consider using this tool to inform clinical
49 decisions as we conduct further studies to determine whether the tool enhances physician decisions and
50 improves patient outcomes.

51 **Primary Funding Source:** Spanish Ministry of Health, Catalonia Govern, Fundació Marató-TV3.

52 **Keywords:** acute heart failure, risk score, outcomes.

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56 **Introduction**

57 Annual hospital admissions due to acute heart failure (AHF) in Europe and the USA exceed 1 million in each
58 region and account for most of the costs of heart failure-related care (1, 2). The emergency department (ED)
59 has a central position in the management of AHF, since about 90% of patients with this condition attend an ED
60 to improve their symptoms (3, 4). Once initial treatments have been administered in the ED and their effects
61 checked, decisions are made regarding subsequent patient management: specifically does the patient need to
62 be hospitalized or can they be discharged home with proper treatment and follow-up. As a result of a mainly
63 subjective, empirically-driven assessment, a highly variable proportion of AHF patients is currently being
64 directly discharged to home from ED: 16.3% in US (5), 23.9% in Spain (4), and 36.2% in Canada (6).

65 Although decision-making in the ED is of critical importance, emergency physicians currently are not stratifying
66 patient by risk during this process. Some biomarkers, for example, heart-specific markers like natriuretic
67 peptides and troponin or non-specific markers like glucose or creatinine, are associated with prognosis, but
68 cannot by themselves predict outcomes with sufficient reliability to aid decision-making (7,8). Alternatively,
69 several AHF risk scores have been developed (9,10), but these scores have been based on hospitalized patients
70 thus ignoring the many AHF patients, more than a third in certain countries (6), who are entirely managed in
71 the ED and discharged home. To our knowledge, only 3 risk scores have been developed specifically for use in
72 the ED: 2 in Canada (the Ottawa Heart Failure Risk Scale, OHFRS, and the Emergency Heart Failure Mortality
73 Risk Grade, EHMRG) (11,12) and 1 in United States (The Improving Heart Failure Risk Stratification in the
74 Emergency Department, STRATIFY, scale) (13). However, some were not externally validated (OHFRS,
75 STRATIFY), some were constructed from administrative data (OHFRS, EHMRG), some excluded a substantial
76 portion of patients (EHMRG: palliative patients excluded; OHFRS: non-consecutive sample with multiple
77 exclusion criteria), and some were derived from databases of limited size (OHFRS: 557 patients; STRATIFY:
78 1033 patients). Therefore, we believe there is a need for additional tools to help physicians in the ED stratify
79 patients with acute heart failure (AHF) according to risk.

80 **Methods**

81 The Acute Heart Failure in Emergency Departments (EAHFE) Registry

82 The EAHFE Registry collects detailed information on consecutive patients attending 34 Spanish EDs with a final
83 diagnosis of AHF (14,15). Hospitals participate in the EAHFE Registry voluntarily, and they include university
84 and community hospitals, EDs with high, medium or low volume of attendances (>300, 200-300, or <200/day,
85 respectively), and hospitals from all areas of the country. Attending emergency physicians use Framingham's
86 clinical diagnostic criteria (16) to identify patients for the registry. Thereafter, the diagnosis is double-checked
87 by the principal investigator of each centre, who makes the final adjudication of AHF diagnosis based on the
88 review of medical charts and all complementary tests done during the ED stay and any hospitalization. The
89 diagnosis was confirmed by natriuretic peptide determinations or echocardiography (17) in the 92% of
90 patients included in the EAHFE Registry. The only exclusion criteria was patients that had a concurrent
91 diagnosis of ST-elevation myocardial infarction, which occurred in approximately 3% of patients.

92 For every patient, data on demographics, clinical history, presentation and treatments were routinely collected
93 on specific case record forms. Interventions, treatments and patient placements (hospital admission or
94 discharge) were entirely based on the decision-making of the attending emergency physician. Subsequent
95 follow-up, through telephone contact and consultation of medical records, was performed between day 31
96 and 90. The EAHFE Registry complies with the Declaration of Helsinki and was approved by the Ethical
97 Committees of all participating centres, and all patients gave informed consent. Around 2% of patients fulfilling
98 inclusion and exclusion criteria refused to participate.

99 Study design

100 During the design of the EAHFE Registry, we planned to develop a model that could stratify patients according
101 to their risk of experiencing adverse outcomes. We wanted this model to be used as soon as possible after
102 arrival in the ED by the first emergency physician who saw the patient using variables routinely available in
103 most EDs. We named this model MEESSI-AHF (Multiple Estimation of risk based on the Emergency department
104 Spanish Score In patients with AHF).

105 When developing the model, we selected registry patients from May 2009 and November-December 2011 for
106 the derivation cohort and patients from January-February 2014 for the validation cohort (Figure S1). We used
107 patients in the derivation cohort to generate a 30-day mortality risk model and we used patients from the
108 validation cohort to measure how stable the model was.

109 Data analysis

110 We first identified over 88 candidate predictor variables (Supplemental Table S1) that described baseline
111 demographics, medical history and status at admission and could potentially have prognostic implications. To
112 develop the risk score, we used logistic regression (without interaction terms) with checks for non-linearity
113 and forward stepwise variable selection with an entry criterion of $p < 0.010$. We used multiple imputation with
114 chained equations (18) to produce 50 imputed data sets for estimating missing values. Once we identified a
115 predictor, we then identified a cut-off value based on our clinical information about the predictor's value (e.g.,
116 serum potassium) or about the linear trend (e.g., serum creatinine and systolic blood pressure). In the final
117 model, we formed each continuous variable into ordered categories to facilitate their use in practice. We
118 measured the model's discrimination with the c-statistic, and we measured the model's calibration by
119 comparing observed- versus model-derived mortality risk with the Hosmer-Lemeshow statistic. We conducted
120 sensitivity analyses by type of hospital (university vs community), by daily ED census (low-medium vs high
121 volume), and for alternative models that did not include values for Barthel index, NT-proBNP, or troponin (in
122 any combination) as they can be lacking in some circumstances and/or certain EDs. We compared our model
123 with the EHMRG model (12) in a merged data set of both derivation and validation cohorts by comparing the
124 areas under the ROC curves for 30-day mortality with the DeLong test. We used STATA software, version 13.1
125 (Stata Corp, College Station, TX, USA) for all analyses.

126 Role of the funding source

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130 role in the design, conduct, and analysis of this study or in the decision to submit the manuscript for
131 publication.

132

133 **Results**

134 The study derivation cohort comprises 4897 consecutive patients admitted to an ED with AHF during May 2009
135 and Nov-Dec 2011 (Figure S1). Thirty patients were excluded from analysis due to lack of follow-up, while
136 those with censored data (48 patients with <30 days of follow-up) were included. Patients had a mean age
137 79.7 years, 57.1% were females, comorbidities were very frequent (83.4% had hypertension, 42.2% diabetes
138 mellitus, 39.4% dyslipidemia, 29.9% ischemic cardiomyopathy), 89.5% had New York Heart Association (NYHA)
139 class III-IV and 56.5% had some dependency (Barthel index <100 points) at ED arrival, and 41.5% patients had
140 LVEF below 50%, with 52.4% of them receiving beta-blockers, 62.9% angiotensin-converter enzyme inhibitor or
141 angiotensin-II receptor blocker, and 29.1% mineralocorticoid-receptor antagonist. Patients subsequently
142 hospitalized (75.6%) had a median length of stay of 7 days. The rest of the characteristics of the study
143 population are presented in Table 1.

144 Within 30 days of admission, 500 patients (10.3%) had died. From all of the candidate predictors, a logistic
145 regression model was used with forward stepwise variable selection to identify the final 13 highly significant
146 independent death predictors included into the MEESI-AHF risk score. These variables are listed in Table 1
147 ordered by their statistical strength of prediction (i.e. Barthel index at admission is the most highly significant)
148 and each odds ratio is adjusted for all the other variables. Figure S2 displays the independent impact of each
149 predictor on mortality risk based on the model in Table 1, and Table S2 shows comparison in key predictor
150 variables in patient with and without missing values.

151 For any patient, one adds together their relevant risk coefficients plus the intercept coefficient in Table 1 to
152 determine the multivariable risk score, which is the patient's predicted log (odds) of dying within 30 days. The
153 distribution of this risk score for all 4867 patients is shown in Figure 1. Also, the curve in Figure 1 relates a
154 patient's risk score to the probability of dying within 30-day of admission, which ranges from 0.005 to 0.898
155 with a median of 0.051. To facilitate the calculation of any patient's risk of dying within 30 days, we have set
156 up a website <http://MEESI-AHF.risk.score-calculator-ica-semes.portalsemes.org> : For a specific patient one
157 enters the relevant 13 items and immediately their predicted % risk of dying within 30 days is provided.

158 Figure 2 shows the cumulative mortality over 30 days for patients classified into 6 risk groups: the bottom 4
159 quintiles and the top two deciles of the risk score's distribution in this derivation cohort. Good discrimination
160 of the model was achieved, with c-statistic 0.836 (95% CI 0.818 -0.853). There was a steep gradient in 30-day

161 mortality across risk groups: with 45% mortality for the top decile of risk and around 0.7% for the bottom
162 quintile of risk. Similar discrimination capacity was observed in either university or community hospitals, as
163 well as in low-medium or high-volume ED (Table 2). In this derivation cohort Figure 3(a) depicts the model
164 goodness-of-fit, comparing observed and model-predicted 30-day mortality risk across the 6 risk groups. A
165 useful nomenclature is as follows: low risk (first and second quintiles), intermediate risk (third and fourth
166 quintiles), high risk (next decile) and very high risk (top decile). Sensitivity and specificity of the every risk
167 threshold for each category plotted on a ROC curve is presented in Figure S3. Reduced models lacking Barthel
168 index, troponin or NT-proBNP (in any combination) also showed good discriminatory capacity, ranging from
169 0.829 and 0.784 (Table S3), and these incomplete models have been also incorporated in the website
170 calculator.

171 Finally, we used 3229 patients recruited during Jan-Feb 2014 to validate our risk score on an external
172 population of patients, 299 (9.26%) dying within 30 days of ED admission. Five patients of the validation cohort
173 were excluded from analysis due to lack of follow-up, while six patients with less than 30 days follow-up were
174 included. Comparisons for key predictor variables between derivation and validation cohorts are shown in
175 Table S4. Distribution of the MEESSEI-AHF scores is presented in Figure S4. In this validation cohort, Figure 3(b)
176 compares the observed and model-predicted mortality in six risk groups (from lowest quintile to top decile).
177 The model fit and extent of risk discrimination is very similar to what was found in the derivation cohort. The c-
178 statistic in the validation cohort is 0.828 (95% CI 0.802-0.853), very similar to that achieved in model
179 development. To check goodness of model fit, the Hosmer-Lemeshow test for the derivation cohort was
180 $P=0.99$, and for the validation cohort $P=0.122$. When compared with the previously developed risk score
181 EHMRG intended for 7-day mortality prediction (12) using a same sample of patients for both calculations, the
182 MEESSEI-AHF had superior discrimination overall (c-statistic, 0.830 vs. 0.750; $P<0.001$; Figure S5).

183

184 **Discussion**

185 The findings we present in this study are based on a large prospective population-based cohort of consecutive
186 AHF patients admitted to 34 hospital EDs across Spain. Patients with many types of AHF were included, except
187 for those developing AHF during an ST-elevation myocardial infarction, and all data were recorded shortly after

188 arrival in the ED. The 13 predictors of 30-day mortality we identified should all be promptly available in routine
189 clinical practice worldwide; and we have provided a web calculator ([http://MEESSI-AHF.risk.score-calculator-](http://MEESSI-AHF.risk.score-calculator-ica-emes.portalsemes.org)
190 [ica-emes.portalsemes.org](http://MEESSI-AHF.risk.score-calculator-ica-emes.portalsemes.org)) to make it easier for physicians to calculate the risk for a specific patient. Using
191 such a calculator, emergency physicians will now be able to determine whether a patient is at high (or low) risk
192 of dying within 30 days which, in turn, might allow for better patient management. Our score may be
193 particularly useful in the 10% of patients at very high risk for 30-day mortality (around a 45%), as well as in the
194 40% of patients at low risk for 30-day mortality (<2%). Identification of both groups has important
195 management implications. For a patient with very high risk, special attention has to be focused on ensuring
196 that the patient and relatives are aware of the severity and, assuming they are appropriate, on prompt
197 aggressive treatments with an emphasis on early admission to an intensive care unit. For a patient with low
198 risk, attention should be focused on treatment that will lead to early discharge from the ED to home, which is
199 consistent with a recent consensus about patients with <2% all-cause mortality as long as they are observed
200 long enough in the ED (19).

201 In the US, the overall incidence rate of heart failure hospitalizations has declined 29.5% between 1998 and
202 2007 (20). We suggest that this decline could be due to better ambulatory care that avoids patient
203 decompensation and allows proper treatment of less severe AHF episodes without hospital admission. In this
204 sense, there is an increasing perception that more AHF patients at low risk of adverse outcomes should avoid
205 hospitalization (4, 21), and recent consensus opinions by clinical experts advocate that approach (19,22).
206 Specifically, one group recommends rates of 20% to 40% direct ED discharge for patients being diagnosed with
207 AHF (depending whether the ED lacks or possesses, respectively, a specific observation area) (19). These
208 figures match well to patients in our low risk category (40%). Avoiding hospital admission is not only a matter
209 of health care system efficiency improvement that could save substantial costs. Hospitalization itself could
210 imply some potential hazards: nosocomial infection, increased errors in patient with polypharmacy, acute
211 reactive psychosis and deteriorating functional status are quite common amongst the elderly being
212 hospitalized. AHF patients are typically of advanced age, with a median age around 80 years in most series
213 (4,12) (median 80 years in our cohort). However, we are not aware of any formal tools that are currently being
214 used to aid ED risk stratification for AHF patients. Thus, some authors have argued that direct discharge of
215 patients without objectively-based risk stratification is putting some patients at an unacceptably high risk of

216 adverse events (6,23). This situation contrasts with improvements achieved in other high prevalent ED
217 conditions, such as community-acquired pneumonia and acute coronary syndromes, where risk scores have
218 been developed (24,25) and are being widely applied to discharge less severe patients who previously would
219 have been admitted to hospital. We believe that the MEESI-AHF risk score can provide similar help in the
220 management of patients with AHF, especially for elderly patients who are more challenging to evaluate (15).

221 All 13 variables we found to be predictive have been repeatedly reported as influencing the prognosis of
222 patients with AHF (1,11-13,15,26-28). However, in our study 4 of these variables had more than 25% missing
223 values. We adjusted for these missing values using a multiple imputation technique. Moreover, in order to
224 match our score to what happens when real patients are in EDs, our website calculator provides a risk score
225 even when values for Barthel index, troponin levels, and NT-ProBNP are not available and we have shown that
226 these risk scores perform as well as the regular risk scores (Table S4).

227 Our model compares favourably with other risk models. For example, our model had a c-statistic of 0.836 in
228 the derivation cohort and 0.828 in the validation cohort, which were higher than the comparable value when
229 we calculated the EHMRG score in 2137 patients who had all the data necessary to calculate an EHMRG score.
230 The EHMRG model focused on a shorter-term perspective (7-day mortality) (12). We feel a longer perspective
231 (30-day mortality) provides a better framework to create a model to aid emergency physicians. Moreover,
232 EHMRG score excluded palliative patients (who have a higher risk of adverse events), and that could limit its
233 generalizability. Patients only receiving palliative care are not uncommon: e.g. 10.2% of our patients had a
234 Barthel index of 0 to 20 points (indicating complete dependence) and an additional 32.8% had a Barthel index
235 between 21 and 60 points (indicating severe dependence) and, although not directly recorded in our study, for
236 many of them palliative care could apply. However, we have previously demonstrated that the exclusion of
237 patients for whom palliative care could potentially apply did not significantly change the discriminatory
238 capacity of the model (only decreased from 0.741 to 0.729) (29). Our findings, in line with previous works in
239 this field (30), affirm that the Barthel index is a key outcome predictor, adding value to previously developed
240 risk scores. Thus, it is important to recognize that patient frailty and dependence are key aspects that should
241 be considered in every disease impacting on an elderly population, as it comes about AHF patients. Finally, our
242 model has been developed using data prospectively recorded using a standardised pro forma at the time of
243 admission to the ED, instead of using retrospective extraction from administrative reports, as was done for the

244 EHMRG model. The latter strategy could limit reliability and completeness of data. All the above-mentioned
245 limitations, even with more extensive patient exclusion criteria and smaller sample, also apply for the OHFRS
246 model, which obtained a c-statistic of 0.77 (11). On the other hand, although the STRATIFY score (13) was
247 developed using data recorded prospectively, it was derived with a limited number of cases, no external
248 validation was done, and got moderate discriminatory capacity (c-statistic: 0.68) (13). Therefore, for the first
249 time, we offer a risk-model with robust data from a large-scale population-based study to quickly assess
250 patient prognosis.

251 Our study has important limitations. Some important predictors had a high number of missing values, which
252 we have addressed with multiple imputation techniques and sensitivity analyses. There is a possibility of a
253 “false positive” predictor entering the risk model after testing 88 candidate predictor variables, although use
254 of $p < 0.01$ as entry criterion has minimised this risk. Some variables, e.g. Barthel index, NYHA class, association
255 with ACS, or low cardiac output, are partially based on subjective interpretation, but we tried to reduce this
256 problem by providing all research centers with a dictionary for all variables and holding meetings with all
257 researchers just before each recruitment phase in an attempt to minimize inconsistency. Additionally, the
258 precision of our model might change in the future, especially if new treatments for heart failure were able to
259 modify mortality, such as angiotensin II receptor blocker neprilysin inhibitors, which were not available when
260 this study was performed. Finally, as for any study in a single country, caution should be taken in extrapolating
261 findings internationally. Moreover, EDs were not randomly selected but were participants of the EAHFE
262 Registry, with special interest in AHF, so it is possible results could differ when applied to other EDs. Thus, we
263 encourage others to explore validation of our risk model in other countries/regions. Nonetheless, we believe
264 that our model has the potential for being used widely.

265 In conclusion, our study demonstrates that physicians can use 13 readily available items to estimate individual
266 risk of 30-day mortality for patients with AHF who are admitted to the ED. With strong risk discrimination,
267 good model fit and external validation, this tool is now ready for clinical use. Further study is needed to
268 elucidate the real potential of the MEESSI-AHF risk score for enhancing physician behaviour and improving
269 patient outcomes. We have provided user-friendly access to a way of calculating scores for specific patients
270 (<http://MEESSI-AHF.risk.score-calculator-ica-semes.portalsemes.org>). This tool has excellent discrimination
271 and calibration, and it was validated in patients different from the patients used to develop it. We think

272 physicians can consider using this tool to inform clinical decisions as we conduct further studies to determine
273 whether the tool enhances physician decisions and improves patient outcomes. We believe that this tool will
274 be especially useful for identifying individuals at lower risk for whom further hospitalization may be not
275 required.

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- 379

Table 1: A multivariable predictive model for 30-day mortality using logistic regression in 4867 patients.

Variable	No. of patients (%)	30-day mortality (%)	OR (95% CI)*	% missing
Barthel index at admission				28.4%
≥75	1556 (44.6%)	60 (3.9%)	1	
50-74	912(26.2%)	76 (8.3%)	1.52 (1.07-2.16)	
25-49	614 (17.6%)	98 (16.0%)	2.34 (1.61-3.38)	
<25	404 (11.6%)	125 (30.9%)	3.99 (2.69-5.92)	
Systolic blood pressure (mm Hg)				2.0%
≥155	1443 (30.3%)	89 (6.2%)	1	
140-154	991 (20.8%)	81 (8.2%)	1.52 (1.08-2.15)	
125-139	986 (20.7%)	105 (10.7%)	2.06 (1.48-2.86)	
110-124	845 (17.7%)	114 (13.5%)	2.56 (1.85-3.56)	
95-109	357 (7.5%)	56 (15.7%)	2.52 (1.67-3.78)	
<95	146 (3.1%)	41 (28.1%)	3.03 (1.82-5.06)	
Age (years)				0.3%
<75	1227 (25.3%)	61 (5.0%)	1	
75-79	911 (18.8%)	71 (7.8%)	1.59 (1.08-2.33)	
80-84	1116 (23.0%)	112 (10.0%)	1.74 (1.22-2.49)	
85-89	1054 (21.7%)	139 (13.2%)	1.72 (1.21-2.45)	
>=90	546 (11.3%)	117 (21.4%)	2.62 (1.79-3.83)	
NT-proBNP (pg/mL)				59.8%
<8000	1412 (72.2%)	84 (6.0%)	1	
8000-15999	285 (14.6%)	38 (13.3%)	1.64 (1.08-2.49)	
16000-23999	110 (5.6%)	26 (23.6%)	2.04 (1.25-3.34)	
>24000	148 (7.6%)	42 (28.4.1%)	2.59 (1.68-3.99)	
Potassium (mEq/L)				4.9%
<3.5	249 (5.4%)	32 (12.9%)	1.48 (0.95-2.30)	
3.5-4.9	3536 (76.5%)	284 (8.0%)	1	
5-5.5	508 (11.0%)	73 (14.4%)	1.35 (0.98-1.87)	
>5.5	332 (7.2%)	78 (23.5%)	2.09 (1.48-2.94)	
Positive troponin level	1286 (45.1%)	198 (15.4%)	1.75 (1.32-2.30)	41.4%
NYHA class IV at admission	2148 (46.1%)	340 (15.8%)	1.63 (1.28-2.09)	4.2%
Respiratory rate (breaths/min)				29.5%
<25	2305 (67.2%)	189 (8.2%)	1	
25-29	540 (15.7%)	76 (14.1%)	1.35 (0.96-1.88)	
>=30	585 (17.1%)	109 (18.6%)	1.69 (1.23-2.32)	
Low output symptoms*	792 (17.5%)	161 (20.3%)	1.48 (1.15-1.90)	6.9%
Oxygen saturation (%)				4.0%
95-100	1830 (39.2%)	127 (6.9%)	1	
90-94	1675 (35.8%)	159 (9.5%)	1.19 (0.90-1.56)	
84-89	689 (14.7%)	98 (14.2%)	1.34 (0.97-1.86)	
<85%	479 (10.3%)	98 (20.5%)	1.67 (1.18-2.36)	
Episode associated with ACS**	134 (2.8%)	36 (26.9%)	2.02 (1.25-3.27)	2.9%
Hypertrophy at ECG***	290 (6.2%)	38 (13.1%)	1.59 (1.05-2.40)	3.4%
Creatinine (mg/dL)				1.8%
<1.5	3401 (71.1%)	263 (7.7%)	1	
1.5-2.4	1054 (22.1%)	156 (14.8%)	1.27 (0.99-1.64)	
>=2.5	326 (6.8%)	67 (20.6%)	1.46 (1.00-2.13)	

381 ACS is acute coronary syndrome; ECG, electrocardiogram; NYHA, New York Heart Association; OR, odds ratio.

382 * Defined by confusion, weakness, cold periphery and any sign: poor peripheral perfusion, anuria or oliguria.

383 **Defined by the presence of at least two of the following three criteria: symptoms of chest pain, ECG abnormalities, and positive troponin.

384 ***Defined by the Sokolow-Lyon index.

385 ‡ Multivariable predictive model for 30-day mortality using logistic regression. Each quantitative predictor variable has been grouped
386 into appropriate categories. The odds ratio for each category is the change in the odds of dying within 30 days relative to the reference
387 category (e.g. age<75 years). The coefficient for each variable can be obtained as the log (odds ratio). Multiple imputation using
388 chained was used for missing data.

389 † The intercept was -5.40, which is the log (odds) of dying within 30 days for a patient who is in the reference category of every
390 variable. Such a patient has the most favourable characteristics possible and has a very low probability (0.5%) of dying within 30 days.
391

392 **Table 2** - Analysis of 30-day mortality stratified by type of hospital (university vs community) and ED volume of
 393 attendances (low-medium vs high volume)

394

Risk Quintile	30-day mortality in university hospitals	30-day mortality in community hospitals	P-value*	30-day mortality in high-volume ED	30-day mortality in low/medium-volume ED	P-value**
Bottom quintile	6 (0.7%)	1 (0.7%)	0.65	2 (0.3%)	5 (1.3%)	0.74
2nd quintile	15 (1.8%)	3 (2.4%)		11 (1.8%)	7 (2.0%)	
3rd quintile	50 (5.9%)	8 (6.7%)		36 (6.0%)	22 (6.0%)	
4th quintile	83 (9.9%)	19 (15.5%)		64 (10.4%)	38 (10.8%)	
Next decile	86 (20.5%)	12 (19.1%)		66 (20.9%)	32 (19.3%)	
Top decile	193 (45.8%)	24 (38.7%)		142 (44.5%)	75 (45.7%)	

395 ED: emergency department

396 * P-value for Mantel Haenszel test. The c-statistic value for our model within university hospitals was 0.839 (95%
 397 CI 0.820-0.858), comparable to that obtained within community hospitals 0.812 (95% CI 0.761-0.862). 4193
 398 patients were admitted to university hospitals (presenting 433 outcomes), whilst 626 patients were admitted to
 399 community hospitals (presenting 67 outcomes)

400 ** P-value for Mantel Haenszel test. The c-statistic value for our model within high-volume hospital was 0.842
 401 (95% CI 0.820-0.863), comparable to that obtained within medium/low-volume hospitals 0.824 (95% CI 0.791-
 402 0.867). 3045 patients were admitted to high-volume hospitals (presenting 321 outcomes), whilst 1774 patients
 403 were admitted to intermediate/low-volume hospitals (presenting 179 outcomes)

404

405 **Figure 1:** Risk score distribution (bars) and predicted 30-day mortality risk (line) from the model obtained in the
406 derivation cohort.

407

408 For a patient in the reference category of every variable in Table 1 the estimated log(odds) of dying within 30
409 days is -5.40 (Intercept of the logistic model), meaning that the risk of dying within 30 days for a patient at the
410 most extreme low risk (-5.40) is 0.5%. To calculate any individual patient's log(odds) of dying within 30 days one
411 adds up their relevant coefficients in table 1 on top of this intercept value. Call this x. Then their probability of
412 dying within 30 days is $e^x/(1 + e^x)$. To facilitate this calculation for any patient we provide a website
413 <http://MEESSI-AHF.risk.score-calculator-ica-semes.portalsemes.org>

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418 **Figure 2:** Cumulative mortality for six risk groups. Risk groups 1–4 correspond to quintiles 1–4, with the top
 419 quintile subdivided into two deciles.

Risk	Intervals	N	Probability of dying within 30 days
Low	Bottom quintile	974	from 0.5% to 2.1%
	2 nd quintile	973	from 2.1% to 3.9%
Intermediate	3 rd quintile	974	from 3.9% to 7.0%
	4 th quintile	973	from 7.0% to 14.5%
High	Next decile	487	from 14.5% to 25.7%
Very high	Top decile	486	from 25.8% to 89.8%

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424 **Figure 3:** Assessment of risk discrimination and model goodness-of-fit in six risk groups (4 quintiles and the
425 top 2 deciles) from low to very high risk for the derivation cohort (top) and for the validation cohort (bottom).

426

427 Q1 to Q4 denote quintiles 1 to 4; D9 and 10 denote deciles 9 and 10.

428

429 **Appendix 1:** Full list of participants in the ICA-SEMES Research Group (Research Group on Acute Heart Failure
430 of the Spanish Society of Emergency Medicine).

431 Francisco Javier Martín-Sánchez, Juan Jorge González-Armegol, Juan González-del Castillo, Esther Rodríguez
432 Adrada (Hospital Clínico San Carlos, Madrid, Spain). Òscar Miró, Víctor Gil, Rosa Escoda, Carolina Sánchez,
433 Carolina Xipell (Hospital Clínic de Barcelona, Spain), María José Pérez-Durá, Eva Salvo (Hospital La Fe de Valencia,
434 Spain). José Pavón (Hospital Dr. Negrín de Las Palmas de Gran Canaria, Spain). Antonio Noval, Sonja Rodríguez
435 (Hospital Insular de Las Palmas de Gran Canaria, Spain). José Manuel Garrido (Hospital Virgen de la Macarena,
436 Sevilla, Spain). José M. Torres (Hospital Reina Sofía de Córdoba, Spain). María Luisa López-Grima, Amparo Valero,
437 María Ángeles Juan-Gómez (Hospital Dr. Peset de Valencia, Spain). Alfons Aguirre, Maria Àngels Pedragosa
438 (Hospital del Mar de Barcelona, Spain). María Isabel Alonso, Francisco Ruiz (Hospital de Valme de Sevilla, Spain).
439 José Miguel Franco (Hospital Miguel Servet de Zaragoza, Spain). Ana Belen Mecina, Rocio Merino Genicio
440 (Hospital de Alcorcón, Madrid, Spain). Josep Tost (Consorti Sanitari de Terrassa, Barcelona, Spain). Susana
441 Sánchez (Hospital Rio Ortega de Valladolid, Spain). Pascual Piñera (Hospital Reina Sofía de Murcia, Spain). Raquel
442 Torres Garate (Hospital Severo Ochoa, Leganés, Madrid, Spain). Aitor Alquezar, Miguel Alberto Rizzi , Sergio
443 Herrera (Hospital de la Santa Creu i Sant Pau de Barcelona, Spain). Javier Jacob, Irene Cabello, Alejandro Roset
444 (Hospital Universitari de Bellvitge, L'Hospitalet de Llobregat, Barcelona). Fernando Richard, José María Álvarez
445 Pérez, María Pilar López Díez (Complejo Hospitalario de Burgos, Spain), Javier Lucas (Hospital General de
446 Albacete, Spain). Pablo Herrero, Joaquín Vázquez Álvarez, Ana Alonso Morilla, Andrea Irimia (Hospital
447 Universitario Central de Asturias, Spain). Pere Llorens, Víctor Marquina, José María Fernández-Cañadas,
448 Francisco Román, José Carbajosa Dalmau (Hospital General de Alicante, Spain). Patricia Javaloyes (Hospital
449 Orihuela-Vega Baja, Alicante Spain).Marta Fuentes, Cristina Gil (Hospital Universitario de Salamanca, Spain).
450 Juan Antonio Andueza (Hospital Gregorio Marañón, Madrid, Spain). Héctor Alonso (Hospital Marqués de
451 Valdecillas, Santander, Spain). Rodolfo Romero (Hospital de Getafe, Madrid, Spain). Beatriz Amores Arriaga,
452 Beatriz Sierra (Hospital Clínico Lozano Blesa, Zaragoza, Spain). Enrique Martín Mojarro (Hospital Sant Pau i Santa
453 Tecla, Tarragona, Spain). María Teresa Lorca, Luis Calderon (Hospital Del Tajo, Madrid, Spain). Lisette Travería
454 Bécquer, Guillermo Burillo (Hospital Universitario de Canarias, Tenerife, Spain). Lluís Llauger Garcia, Gerard
455 Corominas LaSalle (Hospital Universitari de Vic, Barcelona, Spain). Carmen Agüera Urbano (Hospital Costa del
456 Sol De Marbella, Málaga, Spain). Ester Soy Ferrer (Hospital Josep Trueta, Girona, Spain).

458 **Table S1:** List of candidate predictor variables and units/definitions.

<p>Demographics</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Age (years) - Gender (male/female) - Body mass index (Kg/m²) <p>Vital signs</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Systolic blood pressure (mmHg) - Diastolic blood pressure (mmHg) - Heart rate (bpm) - Respiratory rate (rpm) - Arterial oxygen saturation (%) - Temperature (°C) <p>Transfer & Triage</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Triage level (severity) - Type of transfer to Hospital - Transfer to hospital with oxygen - Transfer with diuretic, nitroglycerin or invasive ventilation <p>Medical history</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Hypertension - Diabetes Mellitus - Dyslipidemia - Ischemic Heart Disease - Chronic Renal Failure (Creatinine >2mg/dL) - Cerebrovascular Disease - Atrial fibrillation - Peripheral Arterial Disease - Valvular heart disease - Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease - Dementia - Neoplasia - Cirrhosis - Current smoker - Prior congestive heart failure 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Prior echocardiography - Type of ventricular dysfunction - Left ventricular ejection fraction in the most recent echocardiogram (no older than 1 year before patients inclusion) <p>Medical-social history</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Incontinence - Hearing impairment - Social support - Prior falls <p>Status at admission</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Type of acute heart failure - Symptoms of low output - Cold skin - Cutaneous pallor - Delayed capillary refill - Livedo reticularis - Stupor or anxiety - Dyspnea - Ortopnea - Paroxysmal nocturnal dyspnea - Jugular venous pressure increased - Hepatomegaly - Edema - Tachycardia - Third sound auscultation - Pulmonary rales - Cardiomegaly (by chest Rx) - Pleural effusion <p>Scores</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Barthel index at baseline - Barthel index at admission - NYHA at baseline - NYHA at admission 	<p>Precipitating factors</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Any precipitating factor - Infection (precipitating factor) - Rapid Atrial Fibrillation (precipitating factor) - Anemia (precipitating factor) - Hypertensive crisis (precipitating factor) - Non-compliance Treatment (precipitating factor) - Others precipitating factors <p>Blood tests</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Hemoglobin (g/dL) - Hematocrit (%) - Red cell distribution width (%) - White cells (number/mm³) - Platelets (number/10e9/L) - Platelets volume (fl) - Glucose (mg/dL) - Urea (mg/dL) - Creatinine (mg/dL) - Sodium (mEq/L) - Potassium (mEq/L) - Troponin - BNP (pmol/L) - NTproBNP (pmol/L) - C-Reactive Protein (mg/dL) - Procalcitonine - pCO₂ in arterial blood - pH in arterial blood - Lactic acid in blood (mmol/L) - <p>ECG</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Sinus rhythm - Atrial Fibrillation - Left ventricular hypertrophy (according to Sokolow-Lyon index) - Left bundle branch block - Pacemaker rhythm
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3 **Table S2:** Collective descriptive missingness for key predictor variables in the whole both derivation
 4 and validation cohorts.

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Variable (% missingness)	30-day mortality if missing value (%)	30-day mortality if non-missing value (%)	p-value
Barthel index at admission (28.4%)	526 (9.8%)	273 (10.3%)	0.44
Age (0.3%)	0 (0%)	799 (10.0%)	0.40
Systolic BP (2.0%)	18 (10.7%)	781 (9.9%)	0.73
NYHA class IV at admission (4.2%)	40 (11.3%)	759 (9.9%)	0.39
Potassium (4.9%)	45 (11.0%)	754 (9.9%)	0.48
NT-proBNP (59.8%)	478 (10.2%)	321 (9.6%)	0.44
Positive troponin level (41.4%)	335 (9.9%)	464 (10.0%)	0.92
Low output symptoms (6.9%)	29 (8.5%)	770 (10.0%)	0.38
Respiratory rate (29.5%)	213 (8.6%)	586 (10.5%)	0.007
Episode associated with ACS (2.9%)	128 (9.7%)	771 (9.9%)	0.89
Oxygen saturation (4.0%)	30 (8.8%)	769 (10.0%)	0.48
Creatinine (1.8%)	19 (13.8%)	780 (9.9%)	0.129
Hypertrophy at ECG (3.4%)	30 (11.5%)	769 (9.9%)	0.39

6

7 **Table S3:** Description of the AUC ROC for each reduced-model and the full MEESSI-AHF model.

Model	c-statistic (95% CI)
Full model	0.836 (0.812-0.853)
Without NT-ProBNP	0.821 (0.803-0.840)
Without troponin	0.829 (0.811-0.848)
Without Barthel	0.817 (0.797-0.836)
Without NT-ProBNP and troponin	0.812 (0.792-0.831)
Without NT-ProBNP and Barthel	0.796 (0.776-0.816)
Without troponin and Barthel	0.809 (0.789-0.829)
Without NT-ProBNP, troponin and Barthel	0.784 (0.762-0.805)

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Table S4: Comparison of key predictor variables between derivation and validation cohorts

Variable	Derivation cohort	Validation cohort
Barthel index at admission, n (%)		
<25	404 (11.6%)	171 (8.8%)
25-49	614 (17.6%)	286 (14.7%)
50-74	912 (26.2%)	520 (26.7%)
≥75	1556 (44.6%)	971 (49.9%)
Systolic BP (mm Hg), n (%)		
≥155	1443 (30.3%)	873 (27.6%)
140-154	991 (20.8%)	747 (23.7%)
125-139	986 (20.7%)	681 (21.6%)
110-124	845 (17.7%)	570 (18.1%)
95-109	357 (7.5%)	210 (6.7%)
<95	146 (3.1%)	77 (2.4%)
Age (years), n (%)		
<75	1227 (25.3%)	783 (24.3%)
75-79	911 (18.8%)	580 (18.0%)
80-84	1116 (23.0%)	775 (24.0%)
85-89	1054 (21.7%)	657 (20.4%)
≥90	546 (11.3%)	429 (13.3%)
NT-proBNP (pg/mL), n (%)		
<8000	1412 (72.2%)	1060 (75.4%)
8000-15999	285 (14.6%)	195 (13.9%)
16000-23999	110 (5.6%)	61 (4.3%)
>24000	148 (7.6%)	90 (6.4%)
Potassium (mEq/L), n (%)		
<3.5	249 (5.4%)	150 (4.9%)
3.5-4.9	3536 (76.5%)	2397 (78.4%)
5-5.5	508 (11.0%)	311 (10.2%)
>5.5	332 (7.2%)	200 (6.5%)
Positive troponin level, n (%)	1286 (45.1%)	983 (53.5%)
NYHA class IV at admission, n (%)	2148 (46.1%)	1329 (43.2%)
Respiratory rate (bpm), n (%)		
<25	2305 (72.6%)	1575 (67.2%)
25-29	540 (11.6%)	252 (15.7%)
≥30	585 (15.8%)	342 (17.1%)
Low output symptoms, n (%)	792 (17.5%)	628 (19.5%)
Oxygen saturation (%), n (%)		
95-100	1830 (39.2%)	1292 (41.9%)
90-94	1675 (35.8%)	1098 (35.6%)
84-89	689 (14.7%)	398 (12.9%)
<85%	479 (10.3%)	294 (9.5%)
Episode associated with ACS, n (%)	134 (2.8%)	62 (2.0%)
Hypertrophy at ECG, n (%)	290 (6.2%)	61 (2.0%)
Creatinine (mg/dL), n (%)		
<1.5	3401 (71.1%)	2298 (72.3%)
1.5-2.4	1054 (22.1%)	676 (21.3%)
≥2.5	326 (6.8%)	203 (6.4%)

12 ACS is acute coronary syndrome; ECG, electrocardiogram; NYHA, New York Heart Association; OR, odds ratio.

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14

15 **Figure S1:** Patient flow diagram

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19 **Figure S2:** Mortality odds ratios for each variable in the predictive model*.

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21 *Each odds ratio is adjusted for all other variables in the model.

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23 **Figure S3:** Receiver-operating characteristic curve, with predicted risk labelled on the curve.

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26 Receiver operating characteristic curve for risk 30-day mortality. Sensitivity and specificity of the risk threshold
27 for each category of the prediction model are plotted.

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29 **Figure S4:** Risk score distribution (bars) in the validation cohort.

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32 **Figure S5:** Comparison between the MEESSI-AHF and the EHMRG score

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34 Of note, EHMRG score was conceived to predict 7-day and MEESSI predicts 30-day mortality. Between both
35 validation and derivation cohorts, 2137 patients had available data to calculate the EHMRG score and therefore
36 to perform the comparison between risk scores. The c-statistic for our model was 0.830 (95% CI: 0.804-0.857)
37 and for EHMRG was 0.750 (95% CI: 0.719-0.783) (P-value for DeLong test $P < 0.001$)

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